

IPBES TCA Chapter 2. DMR 2.2 Content analysis and mapping against NFF of practical interventions for concrete action / IPBES transformative change assessment

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Description:

The review corresponds to the IPBES Transformative Change Assessment. The IPBES scoping report for the transformative change assessment describes that Chapter 2 should examine the implications of different visions for sectors, sub-systems (including economic/market, financial, political, legal/judicial, educational, indigenous and local systems, and ecosystems) and the interactions between them, at different spatial scales. In this context, an assessment of practical interventions for concrete action has been undertaken to find those that can foster, accelerate and sustain transformative change towards visions, scenarios and pathways to a sustainable world, in support of section 2.3.2.3. on pathways.

Process overview

Protocol

Step 1: Identification of chapters from previous IPBES-related assessments addressing practical interventions for concrete action leading to sustainability

IPBES-related assessments that have suggested or recommended interventions in favour of sustainability have been identified.

Type of analysis/search/review: expert knowledge

Search languages: English

Location and format of the data:

1. Global Assessment of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (Chapter 6: Actions for Decision Makers)
2. Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (chapter 6: Policy interventions and capacity development to operationalize the inclusion of diverse values of nature in decision-making)
3. Thematic assessment report on the sustainable use of wildlife of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (chapter 6: Policy interventions to operationalise the inclusion of diverse values of nature in decision-making).
4. Report on the second Indigenous and local knowledge dialogue workshop for the IPBES assessment of transformative change: Reviewing the first order draft.

Step 2: Compilation of practical interventions for concrete action leading to sustainability

Type of analysis/search/review: compilation of options

Search languages: English

Search terms and sample extracted: 260 hits

Fields extracted: practical intervention, description (the context the intervention has been suggested and/or can be operationalized), actors/stakeholders involved, examples (if any).

Location and format of the data:

2-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR2.2_practical_interventions(A).csv

Treatment applied: Practical interventions were compiled from tables, figures, supplementary material and text, resulting in a total of 260 interventions (hits). The name of the intervention, its description (the context in which the intervention was suggested and/or can be operationalised), the stakeholders involved and examples (if any) were retrieved. Duplicates were removed where applicable.

Step 3: Assign practical interventions into the NFF's triangle space.

The Expert Group on Scenarios and Models of IPBES developed the Nature Futures Framework (Lundquist et al., 2017, Pereira et al., 2020), which represents a diversity of worldviews on nature, including pluralistic values and culture. Each practical intervention was coded according to its

description, revealing its affinity with each of the NFF value perspectives (Nature for Nature, Nature for Society, Nature as Culture) or a combination of two of them.

This affinity was defined on the basis of the description of the practical intervention and an assessment based on expert knowledge of the value attached to nature in this context, i.e. whether it was associated more with intrinsic, instrumental or relational values.

Type of analysis/search/review: expert knowledge

Search languages: English

Search terms and sample extracted: 247 hits

Location and format of the data:

3-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR2.2_practical_interventions_analysis(B).csv

Treatment applied: A scale from 0 to 1 was used, divided between the three main value perspectives of the NFF according to their affinity. The possible interventions for each value perspective were 0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 or 1, corresponding to different levels of association between the number and the specific values of nature. The sum of the three value perspectives had to equal 1. In the event of divergence of assessment between the coders, the final score was discussed until agreement was reached. The practical interventions were then assigned to each of the illustrative skeletons detailed in the table A.1 below.

This resulted in a total of 247 interventions assigned to 6 scenario skeletons (N-N Arcology; N-N / N-S Sharing through sparing; N-S Optimizing nature; N-S / N-C Innovative commons; N-C Reciprocal stewardship; N-C / N-N Dynamic Natures).

Table A.1: Pathways of interventions to achieve plural desirable futures of living in harmony with Nature (Duran et al., 2023)

Illustrative skeleton	Nature value	Description
Arcology	Nature for Nature	People respect and value all life on Earth intrinsically. This world is characterised by extreme land sparing, as vast areas of land and sea are strictly protected. People live in dense self-sustaining urban areas designed to minimise the influence of people in the biosphere.
Sharing through sparing	Nature for Nature and Nature for Society	People have a fairly strong use orientation towards nature, but also value and protect the self-regulating capacity of the biosphere as biodiversity and natural processes provide the resilience that enables humanity to stay within planetary boundaries. While

Illustrative skeleton	Nature value	Description
		sparing space for nature, remaining areas are used intensively, but efficiently and sustainably.
Optimizing nature	Nature for Society	A highly connected world that shares knowledge and technology to maximise efficient and sustainable utilisation of nature's contributions to people while ensuring maintenance of the key ecosystem functions that support them.
Innovative commons	Nature for Society and Nature as Culture	People have built a world of innovative ecological commons and live in interconnected blue-green cities and rural settlements across land- and seascapes. People use their local and traditional knowledge, services and technology, to manage and expand the use of ecosystems and biodiversity also to enhance their culture.
Reciprocal stewardship	Nature as Culture	In this world, values of reciprocity and harmony structure peoples' relationships with nature at all levels of human organisation. Biological and self-sufficient settlements cultural diversity are co-conserved and co-managed across a wide range of interconnected bio-cultural systems.
Dynamic Nature	Nature as Culture and Nature for Nature	Dynamic, connected and biodiverse ecosystems are valued to allow traditional socio-cultural reproduction, spiritual values and connections to be re-established and new ones to be shaped. Society

Illustrative skeleton	Nature value	Description
		accommodates the dynamism of nature through both traditional and innovative lifestyles that takes into consideration cultural heritage and traditional ecological knowledge.

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Definition of files

ID	Name	File type	Size	Description
1	1-IPBES_TCA_Chapter 2_DMR 2.2_practical interventions	pdf		DMR
2	2- IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR2.2_practical_interventions(A).csv	csv		Data(A) list of practical interventions
3	3- IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR2.2_practical_interventions_analysis(B).csv	csv		Data(B) coding of the practical interventions
4	4- IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR2.2_practical_interventions_process	jpeg		Flow chart of the process